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Electrophoretic assembly and electronic transport properties of rapidly synthesized Sb_2Te_3 nanoparticles

Hazal Batili^{a,*}, Bejan Hamawandi^a, Parva Parsa^a, Adem Björn Ergül^a, Rafal Szukiewicz^b, Maciej Kuchowicz^b, Muhammet Sadaka Toprak^{a,*}

^a Department of Applied Physics, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, SE-106 91 Stockholm, Sweden

^b Institute of Experimental Physics, University of Wrocław, Maxa Borna 9, 50-204 Wrocław, Poland

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ABSTRACT

With the recent advances in thermoelectric (TE) technology, there is an increasing demand to develop thick films that would enable large-scale TE devices. Assembly of TE-films from size and morphology-controlled nanoparticles has been a challenging issue that can be addressed by the use of electrophoretic deposition (EPD) technique. In this work, morphology-controlled Sb_2Te_3 nanoparticles were synthesized through microwave-assisted thermolysis, which were subsequently used for EPD of TE films on specially developed glass-substrates. The electronic transport properties were measured in the temp-range of 22–45 °C. The as-made EPD films showed a high initial resistance, ascribed to high porosity and the presence of surface oxide/passivating layers. The impact of two types of small organic molecules -as hexanedithiol and dodecanethiol, on the electronic transport was investigated, resulting in a significant improvement in the electrical conductivity of the films. The XPS analysis suggests that the thiols bind to the surface of nanoparticles through formation of sulfides. Seebeck coefficient in the range of + 160 to + 190 $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ was measured, revealing the p-type transport through the deposited films. Finally, a power factor of about 2.5 $\mu\text{W}/\text{K}^2\cdot\text{m}$ was estimated the first time for p-type EPD films, revealing the potential of the developed nanoparticles and substrate, the small molecule additives and the EPD process presented in this work.

1. Introduction

Our heavy dependence on non-renewable energy sources is the cause of the current energy crisis in the world, and with the increasing rate of consumption of these sources, their availability in long-term will decrease drastically. One simple step for securing a renewable energy source can be the utilization, and thus the reduction, of the waste-heat that we are creating on daily basis via heating in buildings, automotive exhaust, industrial processes, and even in our bodies. Thermoelectric generators (TEGs) are promising devices that can contribute to the sustainable supply of energy via the conversion of waste heat into electricity. Thermoelectrics had not been very popular since they were considered too inefficient to be cost effective for most applications [1]. This changed in mid 1990 s when theoretical calculations showed that nanostructural engineering can dramatically increase the efficiency of a thermoelectric (TE) materials. By tuning and controlling the sizes and thicknesses of nanostructures it is possible to improve the TE properties

of the material [2].

The cooling efficiency and the power output that is generated by TEGs primarily depend on material properties and these critical parameters can be used to calculate the material's figure of merit, ZT. The relation is defined as $ZT = (S^2\sigma T)/\kappa$, where S , σ , and κ are the Seebeck coefficient, the electrical conductivity, the total thermal conductivity, respectively, and T is the absolute temperature in Kelvin. Over the past years, telluride-based compounds have been studied extensively due to their high ZT values around room temperature [1,3,4]. A good TE material is expected to possess a high electrical conductivity and low thermal conductivity to maximize the ZT, however, these two parameters are strongly correlated in large grained materials. However, it is possible to decouple them by engineering the size and morphology of the particles, interface and grain boundaries.

Antimony telluride (Sb_2Te_3 , $\text{Bi}_{2-x}\text{Sb}_x\text{Te}_3$, where $x \geq 1.5$) is a V-VI binary compound with a narrow bandgap, which demonstrates great potential in TE conversion at room temperature especially in low

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: batili@kth.se (H. Batili), bejan@kth.se (B. Hamawandi), parva@kth.se (P. Parsa), adem@kth.se (A. Björn Ergül), szuszu@ifd.uni.wroc.pl (R. Szukiewicz), macko20@ifd.uni.wroc.pl (M. Kuchowicz), toprak@kth.se (M. Sadaka Toprak).

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dimensional forms such as thin films and superlattices [3–6]. The TE properties are strongly dependent on the microstructure and material composition, it is relatively easier to control and optimize these conditions in low dimensional film fabrication processes such as electrophoretic deposition (EPD), sputtering, doctor blading, thermal evaporation, chemical vapor deposition, and thermal diffusion [5,7–12]. In EPD process, the target particles that to be deposited on a substrate are dispersed in a medium and migrated towards the oppositely charged electrode under the influence of an applied electric field. Since no temperature or pressure is applied to the particles during the deposition, material composition is kept unchanged. It is possible to deposit films on semiconductor or conducting substrates with different geometries by using EPD, however, when the substrate is not an insulator, it interferes the transport property measurements by creating an electric short-circuit. To overcome this problem here we present a glass-based substrate which is not interfering with the measurements on the TE films. In our recent work, we reported the details of the substrate preparation via maskless photolithography and Bi_2Te_3 (n-type TE) film preparation, along with the transport property evaluation on these substrates [13].

The utilization of single or small organic molecules as components in electronic devices are currently under investigation for the exploitation of semiconductor and metal nanoparticles due to their size-dependent properties [14]. There are findings revealing that thiolated molecules may positively influence the electronic properties of NP films. This was demonstrated earlier by ethane dithiol treatment of semiconductor PbS films leading to nearly a tenfold increase in mobility [15]. Recently, a similar trend of reduction in the resistance of organic-inorganic hybrid TE films was demonstrated by the use of single thiols (DDT) [16]. The interaction of thiolated surfactants was suggested to be redox type, causing the reduction of surface oxide [17], which may also contribute to the reduction of interfacial resistance between the particles.

There are only a limited number of reports on the application of EPD for depositing p-type TE films of $\text{Bi}_{2-x}\text{Sb}_x\text{Te}_3$ ($x > 1.5$), using rather large (10–20 μm) particles (obtained by ball-milling of commercial powders) that were deposited on metallic substrates, where the substrate interference with the transport property evaluation is a critical limiting factor [7,18,19]. In this study, shape controlled Sb_2Te_3 nanoparticles are synthesized and directly deposited on glass-based substrates via the EPD method. The surface chemistry and the effect of different thiol molecules as activating additives on the transport properties of the TE films are reported, enabling the estimation of the power factor for the first time for p-type EPD films.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

The materials used in the synthesis of Sb_2Te_3 were Antimony chloride (SbCl_3 , 99.95%), Tellurium powder (Te, 99.8%), Oleic acid ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$), 1-Octadecene ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{36}$, ODE), thioglycolic acid ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$, 98%, TGA), tri-butyl phosphine ($\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{27}\text{P}$, 93.5%, TBP). Oleic acid, ODE, and TBP were used as solvents. TGA was used as a shape-directing agent. Methanol and n-Hexane (C_6H_{14}) were used to wash the synthesized particles. The developer, etchant and remover that were used to prepare the glass substrate after the photolithography process were; MF 319, chromium etchant (product no 651826) and AZ 100, respectively. For the substrate cleaning Acetone (99.5%), Isopropanol (99.8%), and MilliQ water were used. All the chemicals were purchased from Sigma Aldrich-Merck, Sweden and used without any further purification.

The EPD media prepared with Ethanol absolute (VWR, 99.8%) and acetonitrile (Thermo Fisher Scientific, LC-MS Grade). After the EPD process, 1,6-Hexanedithiol ($\text{HS}(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{SH}$, HDT, Sigma Aldrich, 97%), or 1-Dodecanethiol ($\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{26}\text{S}$, DDT, Sigma Aldrich, 98%) was dissolved in 2-(1-Methoxy)propyl acetate (MPA, Acros Organics, 99%) and spin coated on the TE film.

2.2. Synthesis of Sb_2Te_3 nanoparticles

The synthesis was carried out using microwave (MW)-assisted thermolysis process (flexiWAVE–Milestone, 1800 Watt; multivessel high-pressure rotor). A stoichiometric amount of each precursor was utilized to meet the molar ratio of 2:3 for Sb:Te to obtain Sb_2Te_3 . The Te-powder was complexed with 6 mL of TBP by heating the mixture at 220 °C for the 90 s using MW power of 400 W under constant stirring using MW synthesizer (Biotage® Initiator +) until all the Te powder was dissolved entirely. In a separate vial, antimony precursor solution was prepared by dissolving a stoichiometric amount SbCl_3 in 16 mL of Oleic acid under continuous stirring for 30 min to ensure a homogeneous mixture, followed by the addition of 8 mL of ODE, and 1 mL of TGA. The solutions were mixed and then transferred to a 100 mL Teflon vessel for MW-assisted heating for 2 min reaction time at 220 °C, then the obtained powder was washed with Methanol and n-Hexane several times and dried overnight at 60 °C in a vacuum oven.

2.3. Substrate preparation and the EPD process

In this study, a glass-based working electrode was prepared via Advanced Maskless Aligner (MLA 150, Heidelberg Instruments) where the desired pattern is exposed on to the photo resist (non-contact) with a focused laser beam ($\lambda = 375 \text{ nm}$). The patterns used in photolithography were designed via KLayout software, shown as pink and white lines in Fig. 3. The glass substrate consisted of soda lime photo mask blanks (3x3x0.06 in.) with low reflective chrome and 0.53 μm thick AZ 1500 positive photoresist layers (G materials, Deggendorf, Germany). Exposure dose of 140 mJ/cm^2 was used to transfer the pattern to the glass substrate. Following the lithography process, substrates were developed for 1 min, etched for 40 s, and kept in a remover bath for a minute. In between the steps they were washed with MilliQ water, and prior to use they were washed with acetone, isopropanol and lastly with MilliQ water. The glass substrates were cut into different pieces for the EPD process. The counter electrode was a sheet of stainless steel which was sonicated in acetone for 5 min to clean the electrode surface.

The EPD media was prepared by dispersing 1 wt% Sb_2Te_3 particles in a 27 mL solution of acetonitrile (25 mL) and ethanol (2 mL). The suspension was sonicated for 2 min with a probe sonicator (Sonics and Materials Inc) with 6 s pulses and 60% amplitude at room temperature prior to the deposition process. To apply an electric field during EPD process, a power supply (Votcraft CPPS-160–84) in constant-voltage mode was utilized, where both the electrodes were connected to the power supply using alligator clips. The working and counter electrodes were connected to the negative and the positive terminal of the power supply, respectively. Electrical conductivity in the glass substrate was achieved by connecting the Cr lines using a piece of copper (Cu) tape. The alligator clip was connected to the Cu tape, which was removed after the completion of the EPD process, to disconnect the Cr lines. The applied voltage was 80 V DC, the distance between electrodes was 1.5 cm, and the deposition time was 2.5 min. When the deposited film was dry, it was spin coated with 100 μl HDT dissolved in MPA to exchange the surface ligands and improve the TE performance of the film (HDT: MPA ratio 1:1). After the spin coating, the samples were placed on a hot plate at 80 °C for 10 min. At a later stage, the HDT used for spin coating was replaced with DDT, where 100 μl DDT dissolved in MPA was used with 1:1 ratio. The samples were dried under the same conditions with HDT coated ones. Then, a highly conductive silver (Ag) paste (Micro Nano, 15–002142) was applied to make electrical contacts for transport property evaluations. Ag contacts were partially placed on the TE film and partially on the glass substrate.

2.4. Characterization of Sb_2Te_3 NPs and EPD films

The crystalline phases in the as-synthesized material were identified by using X-ray Powder Diffraction (XRPD), which was a PANalytical

X'Pert PRO system, equipped with a Copper anode (Cu-K α_1 radiation). Microstructure analysis was performed using scanning electron microscopy -SEM (FEI Nova 200), and Profiler KLA-Tencor P7 was used for the film thickness evaluation.

Electronic transport properties of the EPD films, including the Seebeck coefficient (S) and the resistance, were evaluated in the perpendicular direction to the metallic lines on the substrate (Fig. 3). Electrical conductivity (σ) was estimated from the resistance, using the geometrical parameters of the deposited films. A detailed description of the measurement set-up can be found in our recent paper [16]. The S is estimated through the integral method, in which one end of the sample is held at a fixed temperature while the other end is heated. The TE voltage generated between the two ends of the sample is continuously registered. The slope of the TE voltage vs temperature difference graph yields S ($=\Delta V/\Delta T$). The electronic power factor ($S^2 \sigma$) was calculated using the measured S and calculated electrical conductivity (σ) of the samples. The transport properties of the samples were evaluated at different steps, and the results will be discussed using the following sample designations within the manuscript (Fig. 1):

1. "PS" the glass substrate with patterned metallic lines (measured in perpendicular direction to the patterned metallic lines);
2. "PS + HDT/DDT" the PS after the treatment with HDT/DDT;
3. "PS + EPD" the PS with EPD film of Sb $_2$ Te $_3$ NPs;
4. "PS + EPD + HDT/DDT" the PS with the EPD film after spin coating with HDT/DDT.

The surface chemical composition of the EPD films has been investigated with X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) technique. The non-monochromatized X-ray source with Mg anode lamp (Mg K α line, 1253.6 eV) was used in all analysis. High-resolution photoelectron energy spectra were recorded with AES/XPS system EA10 (Leybold-Heraeus GmbH, Cologne, Germany) at room temperature. Pressure in the chamber during the measurements was less than 5×10^{-8} mbar. The spectrometer energy scale was calibrated using Au4f, Ag3d, and Cu2p lines, and furthermore all acquired spectra were calibrated to adventitious carbon C1s line at 285 eV. The overall resolution of the spectrometer during the measurements was estimated to 0.96 eV as a full width of half maximum (FWHM) of the Ag3d5/2 line. The WSpectra version 8 data acquisition software was used to collect data, and CasaXPS software version 2.3 (Casa Software Ltd., Teignmouth, UK) was used for data processing (deconvolution). To determine surface chemical composition first of all the wide range energy scan was collected, on the basis of which the detailed (high-resolution) scans of element emission lines were performed. The concentration of atoms in the sample was determined on the basis of XPS spectral analysis, considering the presence of individual elements.

Fig. 1. Sketch (not drawn to scale) showing the sequence of samples at different process steps; (1) glass substrate with patterned lines (PS); (2) PS with the treatment with HDT or DDT (PS + HDT/DDT); (3) PS with the electrophoretically deposited Sb $_2$ Te $_3$ particles (PS + EPD), and (4) PS + EPD + HDT or DDT.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of As-synthesized nanoparticles

MW-assisted synthesis has made it possible to fabricate these nanostructures in an energy-efficient, environmentally friendly, and time-efficient manner -within 2 min. Structural analyses of the as-synthesized material was performed using XRPD and the diffraction pattern is presented in Fig. 2. The crystalline phase is indexed to rhombohedral Sb $_2$ Te $_3$ (ICDD: 96-900-7591), and the indexing of crystalline planes is designated on the XRPD pattern in Fig. 2. No additional peaks are observed, indicating a high purity of the synthesized material.

3.2. Microstructure evaluation of substrate and EPD films

We fabricated a glass-based substrate via maskless photolithography in order to eliminate the interference of the substrate with the electrical measurements. With the direct-write process, we can skip the expensive and time-consuming photomask preparation process. Fig. 3 shows a SEM micrograph of the developed glass-based substrate, revealing the success of the lithography.

process, by comparing the design and the obtained patterns. With the adapted exposure and development parameters, it was possible to write 10 μ m wide metallic lines on the glass substrate. The microstructure of

Fig. 2. X-ray powder diffraction pattern of as-synthesized Sb $_2$ Te $_3$ nanoparticles. The crystalline phase is indexed to Sb $_2$ Te $_3$ (ICDD: 96-900-7591) with rhombohedral crystal structure.

Fig. 3. Sketch (not drawn to scale) showing how the transport property measurements were conducted; pink lines representing the Cr pattern on the glass (white) substrate, the black rectangle is the TE film, the gray rectangles on both sides of the TE film are the Silver (Ag) contacts, and the blue arrows represent the measurement probes. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the EPD film was evaluated via SEM and few micrographs at different magnifications are presented in Fig. 4. Sb_2Te_3 particles with hexagonal platelet morphology, and some intergrown nanoparticles were observed. The morphology control was achieved by the use of the TGA as additive in the reaction medium, which passivates the lateral faces of the hexagonal platelets and enable sideways growth. This morphology is favorable to have a large overlap area between the nanoparticles.

3.3. Electronic transport properties

The Seebeck coefficient (S) and resistance were measured as a function of temperature in the range of 22 to 45 °C for the PS + EPD + HDT sample. The sample is bridged between a hot and cold metallic place, while the transport properties are measured perpendicular to the line pattern orientation that assures the elimination of the substrate effect. The voltage generated by the film as a function of the temperature gradient (Fig. 5a) is used to calculate the S . Measurements performed on

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of the electrophoretically deposited thick film of Sb_2Te_3 nanoparticles at different magnifications. Scale bars are a) 100 μm , b) 40 μm , c) 10 μm , and d) 2 μm .

Fig. 5. Electronic transport properties of Sb_2Te_3 (PS + EPD + HDT) film as the function of the differential temperature (ΔT) or the hot side temperature (T_h); (a) (ΔV) differential thermovoltage vs (ΔT); (b) S , (c) resistance and (d) calculated σ as a function of T_h , (T_c is maintained at $22^\circ\text{C}/295\text{ K}$). The measurements were performed in heating and cooling cycles to show the stability of the films with HDT molecular junctions.

the EPD film did not reveal any measurable S , while the EPD + HDT films show values in the range $+160$ to $+190\ \mu\text{V/K}$ (Fig. 5b), indicating the p-type character of the deposited material. There are only few EPD works reporting on similar p-type material [18,19], where the S has been performed on as-made film showing a room temperature value of $+13$ to $+15\ \mu\text{V/K}$, which upon sintering (at 693 K for 1 h) reached a higher value of $+126\ \mu\text{V/K}$ [19]. Sintering provides densification, reducing porosity, thus influencing the electronic transport properties in a favorable.

way. In this work, we achieve a S value of $+180\ \mu\text{V/K}$ for the as-made films, which is about 15 times higher than the earlier value for the as-made EPD film. The magnitude of S obtained on the EPD film developed in this work is close to the S of the bulk sample made through compaction of similar nanopowder, despite its high porosity [20].

The patterned substrate, PS, does not reveal a measurable resistance, and upon HDT addition (PS + HDT) the observation persists. As-deposited EPD film does not show any measurable resistance, despite the intimate interconnection between the nanoparticles due to electromigration.

However, when the EPD film is spin coated with HDT molecules (PS + EPD + HDT), a resistance in the order of 610 to $630\ \Omega$ has been achieved (Fig. 5c), revealing the effect of HDT in interconnecting the nanoparticles through the oxide layer, thus reducing the interfacial resistance significantly -i.e. activating the film. The measured resistance shows a slightly reducing trend while the temperature gradient is increased, which is typical for semiconductors. Using the geometrical parameters (film length of 1.8 cm , width of 1.3 cm and a thickness of $25\ \mu\text{m}$) the σ is calculated and presented in Fig. 5d, which is about 0.9 S/cm . As there is no σ , or power factor value, provided for the p-type EPD films

in the earlier works [18,19] we cannot make a direct comparison of our

results with the films prepared in a similar way. However, with the help of the presented substrate development approach we were able to obtain the electrical conductivity, as well as the power factor on the p-type EPD films for the first time.

In order to demonstrate the versatility of thiolated molecules in the improvement of interconnectivity between the nanoparticles, and thus converting and insulating film to a conducting one, we have performed the same experiments by using a surfactant like molecule -dodecanethiol (DDT). The results are summarized in Fig. 6, where very similar characteristics to HDT treated.

films were obtained. There is a significant difference between the way these molecules interact with the nanoparticles' surface; HDT is capable of directly binding the different nanoparticles due to the presence of thiol groups at the two opposite terminals, while DDT is a much longer molecule with twelve carbon groups and a single thiol terminal aid in the transport through the intercalation of the hydrophobic groups and thus bridging longer gaps between the nanoparticles. The data reveals the similarity of the mechanism these molecules function at the nanoparticles' interfaces.

By using the σ and S , the resultant power factors have been estimated for the first time on p-type EPD films- and are presented in Fig. 7a and b. The electrical power factor ($S^2\sigma$) was

obtained as $2.5\ \mu\text{W/K}^2\cdot\text{m}$ for the films, revealing both the dithiol (HDT) and the single thiol (DDT) molecules leading to similar power factor values in the films fabricated through the EPD process. An important observation after repeated measurements of the films over periods of weeks revealed a

higher stability of the DDT treated films, which may favor its use for

Fig. 6. Electronic transport properties of Sb_2Te_3 PS + EPD + DDT film as the function of ΔT or the hot side temperature - T_h ; (a) ΔV vs ΔT ; (b) S , (c) resistance and (d) calculated σ as a function of T_h (T_c is maintained at $22^\circ\text{C}/295\text{K}$).

Fig. 7. Estimated electronic power factor ($S^2 \sigma$) of EPD Sb_2Te_3 films as a function of ΔT (T_c is maintained at $22^\circ\text{C}/295\text{K}$) with (a) HDT, and (b) DDT treatment.

prolonged durability. Considering the EPD process, without the need of any vacuum or high tech equipment, and no post.

heat-treatment or annealing process, reaching a high deposition rate of about $10\ \mu\text{m}/\text{min}$, the obtained power factor values may be considered promising, showing the potential of the developed materials and the EPD process for TE, and other electronically active surface applications.

When compared with materials prepared through conventional routes, we see that the electrical conductivity values for the EPD film in

this work are two to three orders of magnitude lower, while the S is comparable or even higher [20]. It is known that porosity adversely affects the electronic transport properties. The higher the porosity, the larger is the interfacial area between the TE material and voids, along with the oxidized interface at the nanoscale. Those changes disturb the free carriers by trapping and scattering them more severely as the porosity is increased. Comparison of the results with bulk materials would not be a fair one, as the presented as-made EPD films are made of nanoparticles and molecular junctions. In order to give a perspective, we

may do a comparison of the trends with findings on porous TEs. There is a very recent report focusing on porous TEs based on p-type $\text{Sb}_{1.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{Te}_3$ (SBT), where direct printing of an ink/slurry, and sintering at 500–550 °C was applied to burn out all the organics. The reported room temperature S of the fabricated 3D structures are in the range of +100 $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ to +170 $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$, depending on the temperature and duration of sintering. The σ value of porous SBT materials are reported to be two orders of magnitude lower than the values obtained by conventional methods, due to the porous nature of the sintered material [21]. A similar trend has been reported on polysilicon, where the effect of systematically increased porosity has been investigated on the electronic and thermal transport of n-type polysilicon. The electrical resistivity was shown to increase about ten to thousand times for porosity levels of 62% and 80%, respectively [22]. The higher the porosity, the larger is the surface of the interface between the TE material and voids, along with the oxidized interface at the nanoscale. Those changes disturb the free carriers by trapping and scattering them in a severe way as the porosity is increased. These may help to explain the possible reason of the reduction in σ in the developed EPD films, leading naturally to low power factor values. The developed porous TE platform enables the study of interfacial processes in the TE transport based on the nanoparticle attributes and type of additives used. Further work is needed, and planned, to identify and study the mechanisms to improve the performance of the EPD films (without the use of temperature or pressure processes), by the use of solid/liquid electrolytes, or conducting polymers.

3.4. Surface chemistry studies of the EPD film through XPS

In order to study in detail, the surface chemistry, the role of thiol, and correlate with the resultant effects on the transport properties, we performed XPS studies on the EPD film of Sb_2Te_3 after the treatment with HDT and the resultant spectra for Bi4f, Te3d, S2p, and C1s regions are presented in Fig. 8. A summary of XPS peak fitting results is presented in Table 1. Besides carbon (C) and oxygen (O), antimony (Sb), tellurium (Te) and sulfur (S) signals are detected. Carbon residue on the sample is about 62.13%, mainly assigned to the organic (C–C) carbon. Sb and Te atoms are dominantly in the form of oxides; Sb–O (88.2%) and Te–O (71.9%). O1s peak is deconvoluted to three distinct forms ascribed mostly to carbonyl (74.02%), followed by carboxyl (22.57%), while a small fraction (3.41% of total O) is indexed to metal oxides -which may be related to Sb and Te oxides. Oleic acid used in the synthetic process can cap and passivate the nanoparticles, thereby contributing to the observed C and O content. The N signal is very low (0.69 at%), and is

Table 1

XPS assignments for PS-EPD-HDT film of Sb_2Te_3 .

Sample	BE [eV] [23]	Fraction	Assignment
Sb_2Te_3	62.13	62.13	4.11% C-metal; 78.19% C–C; 9.41% C–O/C–N; 6.62% C = O; 1.67% carbonates
	285		C
	529.44	2.08	11.8% Sb sulfide
	530.89		Sb
	573.73	3.97	88.2% Sb–O (Sb_2O_3)
	576.77		Te
	163.5	12.62	71.994% Te–O (TeO_2)
	529	18.51	91.16% S(0); 8.84% SO_2
	531.03		S
	532.97		O
	402	0.69	3.41% Metal-oxide
			74.02% –O, C = O
			22.57% O–C = O
			Residual solvent

ascribed to the residual organics from the solvent mixture, as there is no other N related chemical in the synthetic process. A strong signal of sulfur (S, 12.62%) has been observed in the film, originating from the HDT treatment. The dominant composition of S is indexed as metallic.

(91.16% of total S), that ascribed to sulfur in Sb–S forming through the interaction of thiols with the NP surface, while the rest to the S–O bonds. It can be speculated that these S–O bonds are possibly due to the interaction of HDT with the oxide surface layer on the Sb_2Te_3 nanoparticles. The results confirm that thiols are part of the EPD films, conjugating to the surface via chemical interactions, thus, making a significant impact on the interfacial resistance as discussed briefly in the transport section.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates a complete bottom-up solution chemical route, starting from the synthesis of p-type thermoelectric material to its assembly into electrically active films on specially designed substrates. A combination of MW- assisted thermolysis synthesis for the nanoparticles and electrophoretic deposition for the film assembly have been successfully utilized. High-purity Sb_2Te_3 in the form of hexagonal platelets was synthesized as assessed from the XRD analysis. These particles were electrophoretically deposited on a substrate in 2.5 min by applying 80 V DC, with a deposition rate of $\geq 10 \mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. As-made EPD films displayed no conducting characteristics, which was significantly influenced by the addition of thiolated molecules. Through the use of thiol molecules (HDT and DDT) electrical conductivity values about 0.9 S/cm has been achieved, due to the capacity of these molecules to intercalate

Fig. 8. XPS survey spectrum, and high resolution XPS spectra of C1s, Sb3d, Te3d, and S2p of Sb_2Te_3 film treated with HDT.

through the hydrophobic hydrocarbon layer and the oxidized nanoparticle surface through the formation of sulfides. Measurements of the transport properties as a function of temperature demonstrated heat activated conduction, while the Seebeck coefficient revealed p-type characteristics for the deposited films. The platform developed here not only enables successful EPD film fabrication of TE materials, but also allows the study of the impact of different nanoparticle morphology and size, molecular linkers, and electrolytes to identify the best performing film formulation for a selected composition of the TE material. The material and the methods presented here may enable large area TE applications as sustainable energy harvesting coatings, as a complementary source to green transition.

5. Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Hazal Batili: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Writing - original draft. **Bejan Hamawandi:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation. **Parva Parsa:** Methodology. **Adem Björn Ergül:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation. **Rafal Szukiewicz:** Validation. **Maciej Kuchowicz:** Validation. **Muhammet Sadaka Toprak:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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